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**THE ECOPEdagogICAL COMPETENCE OF MARIAN EDUCATORS: PROSPECT FOR
ECOLITERACY, ECOPHILIA AND GREEN CAMPUS**

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Abstract

Despite the calls for environmental care and protection in the midst of sustainable development, there still exists an unceasing neglect and indifference resulting to environmental catastrophes both locally and globally. One of the ways to respond to this urgent concern is a critical and transformative environmental pedagogy termed in this paper as ecopedagogy. There is a need to educate the citizens on their critical duty to love, care and protect the environment. Educational institutions especially educators have a herculean role in intensifying the promotion of environmental care. This study sought to assess the ecopedagogical competence of educators in a university. It employed the quantitative and qualitative methods using a survey questionnaire. Most of the respondents were females aged 31-40 years old and from the tertiary department. The data revealed that Marian educators have good experience integrating environmental education topics into their courses or subjects. Grouping the respondents according to sex, however, yielded that they have a low level of eco-pedagogical competence. On the other hand, there is a moderately high level of eco-pedagogical competence when grouped according to school. Marian educators differ in their experiences integrating environmental topics or ideas into their courses or subjects when grouped according to sex, age, school, and years of teaching in SMU. Among the demographic variables, only age shows a significant relationship with eco-pedagogical competence signifying a strong positive correlation between the two. Most of the Marian educators practice the CHSF minute and integrate environmental issues in their class discussions. These assessment results shall serve as a basis for more intensified drive for ecoliteracy, a more focused promotion of ecophilia and a firmer foundation for a green campus campaign.

Keywords: critical theory, environmental education, ecoliteracy, ecopedagogy, ecophilia, environmental pedagogy

INTRODUCTION

The severity and frequency of the natural calamities are real impacts of climate change (Bannari, et.al., 2017). As a response, mitigation and adaptation efforts are being done by various sectors of the society. Different parts of the globe have been conceptualizing and reconceptualizing means to address the phenomenon. In December 2015, countries signed the Paris Agreement, the most important pact for international cooperation to tackle climate change (UNTC, 2015). In the same year, Pope Francis (2015) issued *Laudato Si*, an encyclical on climate change and inequality. He urged everyone to care for our common home. The Holy Father explores social trends and ideologies that caused environmental problems and elaborates integral ecology as a solution to the socio-environmental issues. Every country shall take part in this effort. According to the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC), efforts to reduce carbon emissions especially from the biggest-emitting countries like China, India, Russia, Japan, etc. is doubly needed (Yi, 2022).

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The Philippines, one of the most vulnerable countries to climate change weather events likewise responds to climate change by creating policies such as the adoption of Climate Change Act and the creation of the Climate Change Commission with the aim of accelerating reforms for the management of the accelerating climate change impact in the country (World Bank, 2022). Environmental education is one of the ways to respond to the global nature of environmental problems. It is one of the means to shift the pattern of human development into a more healthy, just and sustainable trajectory.(Clover, 2000).

Re-thinking the meaning and implications of sustainable development is also crucial in the agenda for the mitigation of the effects of climate change. The UN Sustainable Goal 13 aims to take urgent action to combat climate change and its impact. One of the steps is to integrate climate change measures into national policies, awareness raising, and the improvement of education (UN, 2022).

Despite the intensified collective pledge of global, national and local levels to slow global warming, the threat of the devastating consequences of climate change is still impending (Maizland, 2021). Contrarily, the threat is no longer just impending but it is already a reality. The effects are undeniably being felt worldwide. Hence, there is a need for more intensified awareness program as a response to this perilous phenomenon. One of the ways to respond to this urgent concern is through education, specifically through a critical and transformative environmental pedagogy termed in this paper as ecopedagogy.

According to Misiaszek (2018), the critical tenet of ecopedagogy in viewing socio-environmental phenomena holistically through multiple perspectives and disciplines enforces the need for biocentric viewpoints of teaching. Although the framing and objectives of ecopedagogies are diverse and complicated, the important elements of problem-posing teaching methods, democratically real conversation, praxis-based teaching, conflict-based teaching, and teaching spaces as research spaces will all be discussed.

Albeit existing literatures and researches on ecopedagogy, relatively, there is no study yet on the teaching competence of educators on environmental education. This is what this current research seeks to explore.

Environmental pedagogies refer to an education that is concerned with environmental well-being (Misiaszek, 2016) and human well-being within the ambit of sustainable development. These pedagogies unpack the inextricable link between human beings and the environment that houses their existence. Ecopedagogy is an environmental pedagogy that is focused on this connection. It is “centered on understanding struggles of and the connections between human acts which are environmentally harmful and human acts which are rooted in social conflict” (Misiaszek, 2016 p. 589). This suggests the inseparability of the social from the environmental aspect of human existence. The actions carried out by human beings relative to the environment boomerang to them in the form of natural disasters which have social implications.

According to Armstrong (2018), climate change education outcomes enables educators to strategically plan and evaluate program activities. Moreover, climate change literacy makes students aware how humans affect climate and how climate affects humans and therefore take action and mitigate climate change. This is supported by Schelly (2018) who said that environmental education is transformative inasmuch as it explains and encourages patterns of behavior that are environmentally responsible and thus promote environmental sustainability.

Ecopedagogical teaching practices are crucial in a society's response to mitigate the catastrophic effects of climate change as it is both critical and transformative. It is critical inasmuch as it tends to question, reflect on and evaluate existing practices in relation to socio-environmental connections. This is a reaction against current educational ideas and practices that reinforce

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exploitative ways of thinking and doing thereby making education as accomplice in human exploitation of the environment (Ruyu, 2017).

Ecopedagogy is transformative, too, since it aims at changing the world into a better place to live in, not only in the here and now but more importantly, in the future generations to come. The significant role of educational institutions, specifically the educators is of great significance in the realization of the goals of ecopedagogy.

Ecopedagogy is an environmental pedagogy that aims for an environmental education – a teaching that would lead to action from learners, a teaching that encourages learners to engage in environmentally good actions (Misiaszek, 2016). This refers to the essence of ecopedagogy as an education that strives for praxis through the creation of ecopedagogical learning spaces. This is every educator's responsibility. But every educator is also an environmental educator. Thus, every educator must be ecopedagogically competent in order to form socio-environmentally responsible citizens. Indeed, enhancing our ability to learn, to live sustainably, and to love is the only way we will be able to address the ecological and social imperatives we face as we seek to build a fairer, less troubled and sustainable world for our children (Fien, 2003).

This study aims primarily to assess the ecopedagogical competence of Marian educators. The assessment results shall serve as a basis for more intensified drive for ecoliteracy, a more focused promotion of ecophilia and a firmer foundation for a greener campus campaign. Ecoliteracy, a short hand for ecological literacy points to the ability to understand the basic principles of ecology with the aim of sustaining the web of life (Stone, 2017). There is a need for a practice of ecoliteracy learning which includes the management of the learning environment, the use of learning methods and strategies, and the overall learning outcomes that are sustainable community oriented (Guansyah, et.al., 2020).

Ecophilia, literally understood as 'love of nature' refers to the affective and embodied bond between humans and nature (Ruyu, 2017). This speaks of the close relationship between humans and the environment. Human beings are conceived as microcosms as they are reflections of nature. And as reflections of nature, and in fact a part of nature, humans must not only love humans but the place where humans are. This relationship can be nurtured through education. Ruyu (2017) posited that ecophilia is educationally inspirational because it enriches the meaningfulness of human life. Thus, ecophilia can be considered as a guiding idea of education and such education is ecopedagogical.

A green campus is tied with sustainability. It refers to a place where environment-friendly practices and education combine to promote sustainable and eco-friendly practices in the campus. In the study of Stafford (2011), stakeholders such as faculty, alumni and the surrounding community play significant roles in the adoption of sustainable practices. The study recommends that policymakers can engage stakeholders such as faculty and alumni in help increase sustainable practices in the campus. Programs that subsidize campus sustainability efforts might be the most successful at encouraging campuses to adopt green programs. Thus, results of the current study will be a reinforcement of the CHSF program of the university.

Statement of the Problem

With the main aim of assessing the ecopedagogical competence of Marian educators and utilizing the assessment results for a more intensified drive for ecoliteracy, for the development of ecophilia and for a proposal for a green campus, the following serve as specific problems for inquiry:

1. What is the profile of the respondents in terms of
 - a. Sex;
 - b. Age;

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- c. Number of years in teaching, and
- d. Department?
- 2. What is the level of ecopedagogical competence of Marian educators when grouped according to their demographic profiles?
- 3. Is there a significant difference in the level of competence of Marian educators when grouped according to their demographic profiles?
- 4. Is there a significant relationship between the level of competence of Marian educators and their demographic profiles?
- 5. What are the ecopedagogical practices of Marian educators?

METHODOLOGY

This paper employed the quantitative and qualitative methods using a survey questionnaire to assess the level of ecopedagogical competence of Marian educators. Qualitatively, the study looked into common themes in the responses of the research respondents which will serve as bases for the creation of the development of ecoliteracy, promotion of ecophilia among Marians and ultimately the grounding a campaign for a greener school.

The study was conducted at Saint Mary's University, a CICM catholic educational institution situated in the Municipality of Bayombong, Nueva Vizcaya. The respondents were the Marian Educators in all levels. The questionnaire was composed of three main parts. The first part determined the demographic profiles of the research respondents. The second part assessed the level of ecopedagogical competence of Marian educators through a four-point Likert-type questionnaire. The third part determined the ecopedagogical practices, teaching strategies and activities employed by Marian educators relative to environmental education.

Data gathering began with the approval of the University President through the endorsement of the University Research Center. The following were used to analyze the quantitative data of the study:

- 1. Frequency counts were used to describe the demographic profile of the respondents;
- 2. Means and standard deviations were used to analyze the level of eco-pedagogical competence of the teachers when grouped according to their demographic profile;
- 3. The one-sample t-test was used to describe the significance difference in the level of ecopedagogical competence when grouped according to their demographic variables;
- 4. The Pearson correlation also used to describe the significant relationship in the level of ecopedagogical competence when grouped according to their demographic variables

This research was submitted to the Saint Mary's University Research Ethics Borad (SMUREB) for review and approval. SMUREB has the following address and contact information:

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The study is mainly for educational purposes and does not go beyond it. Privacy of the respondents and confidentiality of data is important; hence, the researchers did not mention the names of the respondents in any part of the research. Data collected were used solely for the research study and will be disposed of after the completion of the study. Data stored in paper were secured

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and only the researchers shall have the access to it. The research respondents were not subjected to harm in any way to answer the research survey questionnaires. Their participation was voluntary and they had the right to withdraw from the study at any time. Before the conduct of the study, the informed consent was explained to the respondents and later on administered to them. Their participation in the study which contributes to the development of ecoliteracy, promotion of ecophilia and grounding of the campaign for a green campus involved no risks.

RESULTS

Section 1. Respondents' Demographic Variables

Table 2. Profile of the Respondents

Profile		Frequency	Percent
Sex	Male	56	38.4
	Female	90	61.6
Age	20-30 years old	22	15.1
	31-40 years old	57	39.0
	41-50 years old	47	32.2
	51-60 years old	20	13.7
	32 years and above	33	22.6
Year of Teaching at SMU	22-31 years	39	26.7
	12-21 years	45	30.8
	2-11 years	29	19.9
School	Elementary	14	9.6
	Junior High School	21	14.4
	Senior High School	17	11.6
	SAB	20	13.7
	SEAIT	28	19.2
	SHANS	14	9.6
	STEH	32	21.9
Total	146	146	100.0

Section 2. Level of Pedagogical Competence when grouped according to their profile variables

Table 3. Level of eco-pedagogical competence when grouped according to demographic variables

	One-Sample Statistics			
	N	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean
Sex	146	1.62	.488	.040
Age	146	3.45	.910	.075

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School	146	4.35	2.002	.166
Years of Teaching at SMU	146	2.48	1.052	.087
Overall	146	3.7449	.60417	.05000

Legend: 1.00-1.49 = No Level of Competence; 1.50-2.49 = Low Level of Competence; 2.50-3.49 = Average Level of Competence; 3.50-4.49 = Moderately High Level of Competence; 4.50-5.00 = High Level of Competence

Section 3. Significant difference in the level of competence of Marian educators when grouped according to their demographic profiles

Table 4. Significant difference in the level of competence of Marian Educations when grouped according to demographic variables

One-Sample Test						
	t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Test Value = 0	
					95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
					Lower	Upper
Sex	40.030	145	.000	1.616	1.54	1.70
Age	45.748	145	.000	3.445	3.30	3.59
School	26.250	145	.000	4.349	4.02	4.68
Years of Teaching at SMU	28.481	145	.000	2.479	2.31	2.65
Overall	74.895	145	.000	3.74486	3.6460	3.8437

Section 4. Significant Relationship in t the level of competence of Marian Educations

Table 5. Significant Relationship in t the level of competence of Marian Educations when grouped according to demographic variables

Correlations						
		Sex	Age	School	Years of Teaching at SMU	Overall
Sex	Pearson Correlation	1	.216**	.025	-.096	.034
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.009	.763	.249	.682
	N	146	146	146	146	146
Age	Pearson Correlation	.216**	1	-.059	-.412**	.246**

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	Sig. (2-tailed)	.009	.476	.000	.003
	N	146	146	146	146
School	Pearson Correlation	.025	-.059	1	-.018
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.763	.476	.831	.464
	N	146	146	146	146
Years of Teaching at SMU	Pearson Correlation	-.096	-.412**	-.018	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.249	.000	.831	.512
	N	146	146	146	146
Overall	Pearson Correlation	.034	.246**	.061	-.055
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.682	.003	.464	.512
	N	146	146	146	146

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Section 5. The Ecopedagogical Practices of Marian Educators

Ecopedagogical Practices	Frequency
CHSF Minute	20
Tree planting	9
Backyard gardening	2
Integration of environmental issues in discussions	35
Discussion of green practices	2
Eco-walk	
Solid waste management	
Using eco-friendly products	
Conducting research on environmental concerns	

DISCUSSIONS

Respondents' Demographic Variables

Table 2 shows the demographic variables of the Marian educator respondents. There are more females than males. Nearly three-quarters of the total population comprises the combined 31-40 and 41-50 years old respondents. Consequently, most respondents have been teaching at SMU for 12-21 years and 22-31 years, with 30.8% and 26.7%, respectively. With regard to school, there are 52 Marian educators from the Basic Education Department and 94 from the Tertiary Department. The total number of respondents is 146. At Saint Mary's University, most of the educators are males. This is supported by studies which looked into

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the relationship between gender and the teaching profession. In the study of Tasner, et. Al (2017), the teaching career is dominated by women. Wanchana (2020) likewise stated that were largely female comprising 73.28%. Based on the data provided by Dr. Jose Ramon G Albert (2013), in the cumulative distribution of teachers by age, age group 40-49 and 50-59 compose the greatest number of teachers.

Level of Pedagogical Competence when grouped according to their profile variables

Table 3 shows the level of pedagogical competence when grouped according to demographic variables. There is a moderately high level of eco-pedagogical competence ($M=3.7499$) among Marian educators. This indicates they have good experience integrating environmental education topics into their courses or subjects. Wanchana (2020) also found out that teachers show moderate competence in environmental education. On the one hand, grouping the respondents according to sex will, however, yield that they have a low level of eco-pedagogical competence ($m=1.63$). On the other hand, there is a moderately high level of eco-pedagogical competence ($m=4.35$) when grouped according to school; however, there is a varied description of the eco-pedagogical competence of the Marian educator with a standard deviation of 2.002, indicating a more dispersed response in relation to the mean. Hence, Table 3 suggests that when they are grouped according to sex and years of teaching at SMU, they have little experience; when grouped according to age, they have some experience; and when grouped according to school, they have good experiences in integrating environmental education topics or ideas in their courses or subjects. The educators demographic profile contributes to their capacity to integrate environmental education in the classroom thus affecting the level of eco-pedagogical competence. This is an affirmation of the findings of Francisco (2020) that maturity comes with experience. Gender-related performance and length of service affect the enrichment and promotion of competency. However, an earlier study conducted by Supardi, et.al. (2017) stated that there is no difference in the level of competence when teachers are grouped according to age.

Significant difference in the level of competence of Marian educators when grouped according to their demographic profiles

Table 4 shows the significant difference in Marian educators' eco-pedagogical competence level when grouped according to demographic variables. Table 3 shows the mean level of the eco-pedagogical competence of Marian educators in terms of sex ($m=1.62$), age ($m=3.45$), school (4.35), and years of teaching in SMU ($m=2.48$). Table 4, however, shows a p-value of 0.000 which indicates significant differences in the level of eco-pedagogical competence when grouped according to their demographic variables. Hence, Marian educators differ in their experiences integrating environmental topics or ideas into their courses or subjects when grouped according to sex, age, school, and years of teaching in SMU. This could be due to the various courses or subjects being taught by the teachers. There are subjects like Mathematics or Physical Education that, though possible, it could be difficult or sometimes inappropriate to insert topics about the environment. Another probable reason is the lack of ecological foundation of some citizens including educators (Westover, 2001). Ecoliteracy and the cultivation of ecophilia is based upon sequential goals which start with an ecological foundation with respect to environmental issues. Westover (2001) further said that environmental education should be infused into existing school curriculum via an

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interdisciplinary approach. Moreover, educational initiatives related to environmental education lacked coordination and there are still many structural obstacles for a real integration in curricula and daily classroom work (Corpuz, San Andres and Lagasca, 2022).

Significant Relationship in the level of competence of Marian Educations when grouped according to demographic variables

Table 5 shows the Significant Relationship in Marian Educators' competence level when grouped according to demographic variables. Among the demographic variables, only age shows a significant relationship with eco-pedagogical competence with a p-value of 0.003, signifying a strong positive correlation between the two. The other demographic variables show no significant relationship with the level of eco-pedagogical competence with p-values greater than 0.05. Hence, the experience of integrating environmental lessons or ideas into the courses or subjects is significantly correlated to the age of the Marian educators but not with their sex, school, and years of teaching at SMU. This implies that as an educator ages, he/she is more inclined to integrating environmental concerns in the classroom. The need to strengthen ecoliteracy in the university. The study of Corpuz, San Andres and Lagasca (2022) concurs with this. Further, strengthening ecoliteracy among educators will ensure advocacy campaigns towards attainment of sustainable goals, initiate a genuine love of nature (ecophilia) and foster ecological network. These in turn shall encourage participation in activities that promote environmental consciousness like the CHSF Program and the Green Campus campaign. This is likewise anchored in the CICM Advocay specifically on Justice, Peace and Integrity of Creation.

CONCLUSION

Most of the respondents are female, ranging from 31-50 years old and mostly teaching in the university for 12 – 31 years already. When they are grouped according to sex and years of teaching at SMU, they have little experience; when grouped according to age, they have some experience; and when grouped according to school, they have good experiences in integrating environmental education topics or ideas in their courses or subjects. Marian educators differ in their experiences integrating environmental topics or ideas into their courses or subjects when grouped according to sex, age, school, and years of teaching in SMU. The experience of integrating environmental lessons or ideas into the courses or subjects is significantly correlated to the age of the Marian educators but not with their sex, school, and years of teaching at SMU. Most of the Marian educators practice the CHSF minute and integrate environmental issues in their class discussions. Generally, based on these findings, the ecopedagogical competence of Marian educators is moderately high which implies that they have a good experience of ecopedagogy.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based of the findings of the study, the following are the recommendations: While Marian educators show a good experience in ecopedagogy, it is suggested that a more intensified campaign on awareness of environmental concerns be conducted. There is a need to capacitate the Marian educators on integrating environmental education in their classes through environmental fora. Also, a more intensified campaign of the university's green

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campus policy is suggested. This can be done during the launching of the CHSF Program and be sustained through activities that promote ecoliteracy and advocate ecophilia.

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